

1 **Original Research Article**

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4 ***In vitro* evaluation of cytotoxic and genotoxic effects of Di(2-ethylhexyl)-phthalate (DEHP) on European sea bass**
5 ***(Dicentrarchus labrax)* embryonic cell line**

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20 **Key words:**

21 DEHP; DNA Damage; Cytotoxicity; Genotoxicity; European seabass cell line; Marine litter.

22

23 **Abstract**

24 Marine litter is extensively distributed in the marine environment, and plastic debris, of which litter is mostly
25 composed, can be a major source of pollutants. Among them, Di(2-ethylhexyl)-phthalate (DEHP) is the most
26 abundantly used plastic additive, and it has been reported to affect biochemical processes both in humans and wildlife;
27 however, studies on its toxicological effects on marine organisms are still scarce. In this survey, we studied the
28 cytotoxic, genotoxic, and mutagenic effects of DEHP in European sea bass embryonic cell line (DLEC) by applying
29 specific *in vitro* tests. Results showed a significant decrease in cell viability starting at 0.01 mM of DEHP after 24 h
30 together with a significant increase in apoptosis and necrosis, morphological changes and cell detachment. Consistently,
31 we detected a moderate increase in DNA strand breaks from 0.02 mM, and a dose-dependent increase in of
32 micronucleus frequency from 0.01 mM, accompanied by a significant inhibition of cell proliferation, which suggested a
33 possible aneugenic effect of this phthalate. Our results demonstrate that *in vitro* exposure to DEHP had a dose-
34 dependent cytotoxic and genotoxic effects in DLEC cell line, encouraging further investigation into its effects in *in vivo*
35 and/or *ex vivo* cell systems of marine organisms.

36

37 1. Introduction

38 The emerging issue of marine litter in the marine environment has recently received increasing attention. It has been
39 estimated that around 60 – 90 % of litter is composed of plastic debris (Derraik, 2002; Arcangeli et al., 2018; Campana
40 et al., 2018). Microplastics, which are fragments below 5 mm in diameter or length resulting from the degradation of
41 plastic introduced into the environment, are a persistent form of marine pollution, since they may require centuries to be
42 degraded (Collignon et al., 2012). Recent studies have estimated that this debris has reached maximum levels of
43 892,000 particles/km² in the Mediterranean Sea (Collignon et al., 2012; Fossi et al., 2012). Microplastics accumulate on
44 the sea surface, particularly in the habitat of neuston (Ryan et al., 2009), and one of the main problems is their
45 accidental ingestion by marine organisms. When ingested, these particles can affect organisms due to both their
46 physical and chemical properties (concerning the plastic polymer itself and the additives present) and the persistent
47 organic pollutants (POPs) collected on their hydrophobic surface (Teuten et al. 2009; Andrady, 2011; Andersson, 2014).
48 Plastic is composed by a wide range of different hydrocarbon polymers, often in combination with additives (e.g.
49 bisphenol A and phthalates). Plastic polymers are considered biologically inert, but their additives can leak and leach
50 from the polymers depending on their molecular size, temperature, and pH of the water and other chemical properties of
51 the medium and of the compound (Teuten et al. 2009; Andrady, 2011; Andersson, 2014). Among these additives,
52 phthalates, which are phthalic acid esters, are primarily used to increase the plasticity of industrial polymers and are
53 used in many consumer products (Mankidy et al., 2013). Phthalates are not covalently bound to the polymer making
54 them susceptible to be easily leached from the matrix. Once released into the environment, these compounds have the
55 potential to be transported for long distances and eventually enter the food chain (Mankidy et al., 2013).
56 Recent studies have highlighted the influence of phthalates on multiple biochemical processes, both in humans and
57 wildlife, including effects on reproduction (Huang et al., 2012; Maradonna et al., 2013; Ye et al., 2014), sperm damage
58 (Huang et al., 2012), early onset puberty in females (Wolff et al., 2010; Mankidy et al., 2013), infertility (Tranfo et al.,
59 2012; Mankidy et al., 2013) and adverse pregnancy outcomes (Whyatt et al., 2009; Mankidy et al., 2013), neurological
60 development (Miodovnik et al., 2011; Mankidy et al., 2013), and onset of allergies (Bornehag et al., 2004; Mankidy et
61 al., 2013).
62 Marine organisms are particularly suited and effectively used to evaluate the effect of pollutants in environmental
63 monitoring and toxicological studies, since pollutants tend to accumulate in their tissues and cells and provide an
64 integrated assessment of the bioavailability and of the biological effects of contaminants on biota. Such studies can
65 allow to analyse the cellular responses and toxicological effects of xenobiotics and to evaluate risks to wild organisms
66 and to humans as consumers of marine resources (Benedetti et al., 2015). In particular, cell lines of marine organisms
67 are widely used as instruments for *in vitro* assessment of environmental stressors and to study important aspects, such as

68 epidemiology, molecular carcinogenesis, toxicology, and functional genomics (Buonocore et al., 2005). Nevertheless,
69 studies assessing the mechanical, physical, and toxicological impacts of plastic pollution (Fossi et al., 2012) and the
70 effects of phthalates on marine organisms are still scarce, despite the increasing concern represented by marine litter.
71 Since most marine debris comes from land-based sources (Carlson et al., 2017), inshore species are particularly exposed
72 to the risks associated with plastic pollution. Moreover, the potential effects of plastic pollution should be primarily
73 evaluated on predator species, which are highly exposed to the ingestion of plastic and bioaccumulation of its additives
74 (Rochman et al., 2013). The European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) is an eurytherm and euryhaline marine teleost
75 that inhabits temperate regions and is frequently found in coastal areas, as well as in estuaries and lagoons. Juveniles
76 feed primarily on invertebrates, while adults feed on fishes. This species is of high commercial and recreational value
77 (sport/recreational fishing) and plays an important role in marine trophic networks. *D. labrax* has been widely used in
78 toxicological studies of anthropogenic pollutants due to its ecological importance, easy maintenance in laboratory and
79 high responsiveness of its biotransformation system (Alimeda et al., 2010). To date, the continuous embryonic cell line
80 (DLEC) (Buonocore et al., 2006), derived from early embryos and formed by adherent and fibroblast-like cells, has
81 been shown to be useful for immunological (Casani et al., 2009) and toxicological studies (Rocco et al., 2013).

82 In this paper, we studied the possible cytotoxic, genotoxic and mutagenic effects of DEHP, the most abundantly used
83 plastic additive, on DLEC cell line to evaluate its potential impact on this coastal species. To this aim, we exposed the
84 DLEC cultures to increasing concentrations of the phthalate. MTT and the Trypan Blue assays were applied to evaluate
85 the cytotoxicity of DEHP through possible decreases in cell viability after treatments. The alkaline version of the comet
86 assay was employed to measure the frequency of SSBs and alkali-labile sites induced by DEHP immediately after
87 treatments. Comet assay is a rapid and sensitive procedure to quantify DNA lesions in mammalian cells (Fairbairn et al.,
88 1997; Berni et al., 2008; Meschini et al., 2015a), as well as the DNA damage induced by pollution in sentinel organisms
89 (Mosesso et al., 2012; Angeletti et al., 2013) and by endogenous reactive oxygen species (Berni et al., 2008). To assess
90 DEHP mutagenicity, we applied the Cytokinesis-block micronucleus (CBMN) assay. This test measures the final effect
91 of an exposure to contaminants (Filippi et al., 2018), and it has a high correlation with cancer risk (Souza et al., 2016).
92 Besides **genotoxic effects**, the CBMN test provides better precision, because the data obtained are not confounded by
93 altered cell division kinetics (Fenech, 2000) and has the potential to detect beneficial effects of agents against the
94 genotoxic action of known carcinogens, both *in vivo* (Berni et al., 2012; Grossi et al., 2012; Pepe et al., 2013) and *in*
95 *vitro* (Meschini et al., 2015b).

97 **2. Materials and Methods**

98 *2.1 Chemicals*

99 Leibovitz (L-15) without L-Glutamine, phosphate buffer saline (PBS) w/o Ca and Mg, and L-Glutamine were
100 purchased from Lonza, Italy. Penicillin/Streptomycin, Trypsin-EDTA in Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS) w/o
101 Calcium, Magnesium, and Phenol Red were purchased from EuroClone, Italy. Bis (2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP), 3-
102 (4,5-Dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT), Cytochalasin B (1200 µg/mL), Trypan Blue
103 solution (0.4%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich,
104 Italy. Foetal bovine serum (FBS) was purchased from Invitrogen, Italy.

105 DEHP stock solutions used during this study were 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 200, and 500 mM freshly prepared in DMSO,
106 before treatments. For the latter, its concentration for treatments never exceeded 1%.

107 *2.2 Cell culture and DEHP treatments*

108 For this study, a continuous adherent cell line derived from European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax* L.) embryos
109 (DLEC) (Buonocore et al., 2005), was used. DLEC cells were grown in Leibovitz (L-15) medium supplemented with
110 10% FBS, 1% L-Glutamine, and 1% Penicillin/Streptomycin. Cell cultures were maintained at 20-22°C without CO₂.

111 For cell viability assays, DLEC cell line was treated with 0.01, 0.02, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 2, and 5 mM of DEHP for 24 h.
112 Solvent and positive control cells were treated with 1% DMSO and 100 µM H₂O₂, respectively. Doses of DEHP used to
113 assess DNA damage were chosen based on the results of cell viability assays.

114 *2.3 Cell viability assay*

115 *2.3.1 MTT assay*

116 Cell viability was assessed by MTT. DLEC were seeded onto 96-well microplates at density of 10,000 cells/well and
117 incubated for 24 h at 21°C, to allow cell adherence. Growth medium was then replaced by fresh medium containing
118 DEHP at concentrations previously described and incubated for 24 h. At the end of exposure, MTT was added to each
119 well (0.5 mg/mL), and cells were incubated for an additional 3 h at 21°C. After incubation, supernatant was replaced
120 with 100 µL of lysis solution (10% SDS, 0.6% acetic acid in DMSO) to dissolve the formazan crystals and produce a
121 purple solution. Optical density measurements were obtained using a scanning spectrophotometer DTX 880 Multimode
122 Detector (Beckman Coulter). Readings were made using a 630 nm (background) and a 570 nm filters. Viability was
123 determined in three independent experiments conducted in triplicate for each experimental condition. Cell viability,
124 presented as the Relative O.D. at 570, was calculated using the formula: = Absorbance of treated cells/Absorbance of
125 control cells.

126 *2.3.2 Trypan Blue exclusion assay*

127 Cell viability was also assessed by Trypan blue. DLEC cell line were seeded onto 35 mm petri dishes at a density of
128 10,000 cells/dish and incubated for 24 h at 21°C, to allow them to attach. DLEC were then treated with DEHP and
129 incubated for 24 h. At the end of the exposure, cells were harvested, and 20 µL of cell suspension was mixed with 20
130 µL of Trypan Blue solution (1/1; w/w) for 5 minutes to allow cell staining. Cells were then seeded on a slide and
131 counted under an optical microscope. Viability was determined in three independent experiments. Percentage of cell
132 viability was calculated as the mean of the cell survival in the three experiments.

133 *2.4 Giemsa staining proliferation assay*

134 DLEC cells were plated into 35 mm petri dishes with a final density of 4×10^5 cells/dish. DLEC were treated with
135 DEHP and incubated for 24 h. Then, cells were fixed with cold methanol for 10 min and stained with 5 % of Giemsa
136 solution in distilled water for 15 min, washed in PBS, and air-dried. Cell morphology was observed and photographed
137 under an inverted light microscope at a magnitude of 100x.

138 *2.5 Detection of DEHP-induced cell death by fluorescence staining*

139 To evaluate DEHP-induced cell death, DLEC were seeded onto 60 mm petri dishes at a density of 400,000 cells/dish,
140 incubated for 24 h at 21°C to allow them to attach, and then treated with DEHP for 24 h. At the end of the exposure,
141 DLEC were harvested and, to identify apoptotic and necrotic cells from viable cells, a combination of Fluorescein Di-
142 Acetate (FDA, 0.75 mg/mL), Propidium Iodide (PI, 0.25 mg/mL), and Hoechst (HO, 0.1 mg/mL) dyes were used
143 (Proietti De Santis et al., 2001). FDA and HO are vital dyes that stain, respectively, cytoplasm and the nucleus of viable
144 cells. PI staining identifies necrotic and late stage of apoptotic cells. Cells in early phase (viable-HO stained) and late
145 phase (dead-PI stained) of apoptosis displayed the characteristic pattern of chromatin fragmentation. Approximately
146 500 randomly chosen unfixed cells for each experimental point were microscopically analysed for cell death, and the
147 results of two independent experiments showing good reproducibility and comparable outcomes were considered.

148 *2.6 Single Cell Gel Electrophoresis (SCGE) analysis*

149 The standard alkaline (pH > 13) SCGE, or comet assay, was performed under visible fluorescent light (Tice et al.,
150 2000). DLEC cell line was treated with 0.02, 0.05, 0.2, 0.5, 2, and 5 mM of DEHP for 24 h. After treatments, cells were
151 collected and processed for the assay. In short, 20 µL of the cell suspension were mixed with 80 µL of 0.75% low
152 melting-point agarose in PBS at 37°C and immediately pipetted onto a frosted glass microscope slide pre-coated with a
153 layer of 1% normal melting-point agarose similarly prepared in PBS. One slide for each experimental point was then
154 incubated in lysis solution (2.5 M NaCl, 10 mM Tris-HCl, 100 mM EDTA, pH 10, with 1% Triton X-100 and 10%
155 DMSO freshly added) for 1 day at 4°C. After lysis, slides were placed on a horizontal electrophoresis unit containing
156 fresh electrophoresis buffer (1 M MEDTA, 300 mM NaOH, pH 13) and incubated for 15 min to allow unwinding of
157 DNA. Electrophoresis was then conducted for 20 min at 25 V and 300 mA at 4°C. Subsequently, slides were gently

158 washed three times in neutralization solution (0.4 M Tris-HCl, pH 7.5) for 5 min and examined after staining with 50
159 μ L ethidium bromide (20 μ g/ml). Stained nucleoids were analysed at 400x magnification with an automatic image
160 analyser (Comet Assay III, Perceptive Instruments, UK) connected to a fluorescence microscope (Axioskop 2, Zeiss).
161 To evaluate the amount of DNA damage, computer-generated tail moment (TM) values were used. For each
162 experimental point, a total of 100 randomly selected cells were scored, and the mean of the results of three independent
163 experiments showing good reproducibility and comparable outcomes was considered.

164 *2.7 Cytokinesis-block micronucleus (CBMN) assay*

165 The CBMN assay was carried out with the standard technique proposed by Fenech (1993) with minor modifications.
166 DLEC cell line was treated with 0.01, 0.02, 0.1, and 0.2 mM of DEHP for 24 h. Then, cells were washed with PBS and
167 fresh medium containing 2 μ g/mL of Cytochalasin B to arrest cell cytokinesis was added for 48 h. For harvesting, cells
168 were washed twice with PBS, trypsinized with trypsin-EDTA (0.25%), and centrifuged for 10 min at 143 x g. The pellet
169 was then re-suspended with cold hypotonic solution (0.75 mM potassium chloride). Cell suspension was centrifuged
170 again for 10 min at 143 x g, fixed first with freshly mixed methanol: acetic acid: NaCl 0.9 % (4:1:5) and, after
171 centrifugation (143 x g for 10 min), fixed with freshly mixed methanol: acetic acid (4:1) and spread on a microscope
172 slide. Air dried preparations were made and coded. The slides were stained with Giemsa (5 %) for 10 min. A total of
173 1000 binucleated cells with intact cytoplasm were scored for the presence of micronuclei (MN) for each experimental
174 point. MN is a biomarker of chromosome breakage or loss. For the analysis of cell cycle progression, 1000 cells per
175 sample were scored for the presence of one, two, or more than two nuclei, and the Cytokinesis Block Proliferation
176 Index (CBPI) was calculated as follows: $CBPI = [1N + (2 \times 2N) + (3 \times >2N)]/TC$ where 1N is the number of cells with
177 one nucleus, 2N with two nuclei, >2N with more than two nuclei and TC is the total number of cells examined. Based
178 on this parameter, the percentage of cytostasis was calculated with the formula: $= 100 - 100[CBPI_t - 1 / CBPI_c - 1]$ where t
179 and c are treated and control samples, respectively (Lorge et al., 2008). The mean of the results of two independent
180 experiments showing good reproducibility and comparable outcomes is shown.

181 *2.8 Statistical analysis*

182 Statistical analysis for MTT, Trypan blue, and apoptotic/necrotic cell death assays (treatments vs solvent) was
183 performed by use of χ^2 -test. The analysis of the significance of the Comet test, in terms of differences in mean tail
184 moment between DEHP treatments and the solvent sample was performed by applying the Student's *t*-test for paired
185 samples. The statistical significance in the yield of micronuclei per cell and the cytostatic effect between the solvent and
186 treated samples was evaluated by the Student's *t*-test and the Chi-squared test, respectively. The level for statistical
187 significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$.

188

189 **3. Results**

190 *3.1 Cell viability*

191 *3.1.1 MTT assay*

192 Figure 1A shows DLEC cell line viability at 24 h of DEHP treatment measured by MTT assay. The solvent shows no
193 effect on DLEC cell survival, whereas H₂O₂ (100 μM) was highly toxic with a decrease in cell survival of ~ 65%. A
194 dose dependent reduction in DLEC viability after treatment with different DEHP doses was observed, displaying a range
195 of viability between 71% at the lowest dose (0.01 mM) to 20% at the highest one (5 mM). Decreasing survival rates of
196 all DEHP treatments show a statistically significant difference with respect to the solvent ($p < 0.001$).

197 *3.1.2 Trypan Blue exclusion Assay*

198 Results of Trypan Blue assay are illustrated in Figure 1B. The solvent shows no effect on DLEC cell survival, whereas
199 H₂O₂ (100 μM) was highly toxic with a decrease in cells survival of ~ 25%. A dose dependent reduction in DLEC
200 viability after treatment with different DEHP doses was observed, ranging between 88% and 15% at the lowest and the
201 highest dose, respectively. Survival decrease rates of all DEHP treatments show a statistically significant difference
202 with respect to the solvent ($p < 0.05$; $p < 0.001$).

203

204

205

206 **Fig. 1:** Cell viability in DEHP-exposed DLEC cell line determined by MTT and Trypan Blue assay. **A)** MTT assay.
 207 Results are displayed as a mean of the optical density at 570 nm at each treatment level normalized to the untreated
 208 control (medium). The data are expressed as mean \pm SE of three experiments. *** $p \leq 0.001$. **B)** Trypan Blue assay.
 209 Cell viability is expressed as the percent of viable cells out of the total cells at each treatment level. The data are
 210 expressed as mean \pm SE of three experiments. * $p \leq 0.05$; *** $p \leq 0.001$.

211

212 3.2 Giemsa staining proliferation

213 Proliferation of DLEC was assessed by Giemsa staining (Fig. 2). Data shows that 24 h of DEHP treatment strongly
214 inhibited cell proliferation and affects cell morphology, especially at higher doses, with respect to control cells. DLEC
215 cells appeared to have lost their fibroblast-like morphology and were more jagged at the edges.

216

220 **Fig. 2:** Giemsa staining proliferation assay. After the 24 h treatment with DEHP, DLEC were stained with 5% Giemsa
221 to assess cell abundance and morphology. Cells from medium, solvent, 0.05, 0.5 and 5 mM of DEHP are shown.

222

223 3.3 Cell death analysis

224 The apoptotic response of DLEC cells treated with different doses of DEHP is shown in Figure 3. In the medium and
225 solvent samples, no significant increase of necrotic and apoptotic cells was observed. H₂O₂ treatment (100 μM) resulted
226 in a moderate induction of necrotic cells, otherwise no increase in apoptotic cells was observed. Both necrosis and
227 apoptosis induction were statistically significant in comparison with the solvent ($p < 0.01$; $p < 0.001$) with a higher
228 induction of necrosis respect to apoptosis starting from a DEHP dose of 0.2 mM.

229

230 **Fig. 3:** Cell Death assay. Percentage of apoptosis and necrosis in DLEC cells treated with DEHP for 24 h. Data are
231 presented as means \pm SE of two independent experiments for each treatment. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$.

232

233 3.4 Comet assay

234 Results of induction in DNA primary damage obtained in DLEC cells treated with DEHP are shown in Figure 4.
235 Control DLEC cells show a mean tail moment (TM) of 0.77. Treatment with solvent did not increase the mean TM
236 value with respect to the medium. H₂O₂ (100 μM) significantly increased the frequency of DNA damage as detected by
237 a mean TM of 4.51 ($p < 0.001$). Treatment with DEHP shows a dose-dependent increase of mean TM statistically
238 significant in comparison with the solvent ($p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$; $p < 0.001$) for all treatments, except that at the lowest
239 DEHP dose (0.02 mM).

240

241

242 **Fig. 4:** Mean Tail Moment in DLEC cell line after 24 h exposure to DEHP. Data are presented as means \pm SE of three
243 independent experiments for each treatment. * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$.

244

245 3.5 CBMN assay

246 Results from CBMN assay are presented in Table 1. No statistically significant difference either in the frequency of MN
247 or in CBPI values in samples treated with the solvent, in comparison to the control, was observed. Treatment with H₂O₂
248 (100 μM) caused a statistically significant increase in the frequency of MN ($p < 0.001$), a significant decrease in the
249 CBPI value ($p < 0.001$), and an increase in the percentage of cytostasis when compared to the medium.
250 With regard to the DEHP treatments, data show a dose-dependent increase in the frequency of MN in comparison to the
251 solvent. Student's *t*-test analysis shows a statistically significant increase in the yield of micronuclei per cell in all
252 DEHP treatments ($p < 0.001$) compared to the solvent. Moreover, an increase in the percentage of cytostasis in samples
253 treated with DEHP with respect to the solvent was found. In particular, lower doses (0.01 and 0.02 mM) display a MN
254 mean frequency between 75.5 to 189/1000 binucleated cells and a percentage of cytostasis between 13 and 9.9,
255 respectively. Higher doses (0.1 and 0.2 mM) exhibit a greater percentage of cytostasis between 67.3 and 73.4, and a MN
256 frequency of 367/1000 binucleated cells at 0.1 mM DEHP. At 0.2 mM DEHP, it was not possible to evaluate the MN
257 frequency due to the high cytotoxic effect of the phthalate at this concentration. CBPI values show a dose-dependent
258 decrease at all DEHP doses with respect to the solvent. The cytostatic effect of all treatments was statistically
259 significant ($p < 0.001$), except at the lowest DEHP dose ($p < 0.01$).

Table 1. Induction of micronuclei (MN), Cytokinesis Block Proliferation Index (CBPI) and percentage (%) of Cytostasis in DLEC cell lines treated for 24 h with DEHP. Data are presented as means \pm SE of two independent experiments for each treatment.

Treatment	Harvesting time after cyto-B	MN/1000 BN \pm S.E.	ts	CBPI \pm S.E.	χ_2	% Cytostasis \pm S.E.
Medium	48 h	4.3 \pm 0.04		1.57 \pm 0.0001		0 \pm 0.00
Solvent	48 h	4.7 \pm 0.15	NS	1.55 \pm 0.0002	NS	3.7 \pm 0.03
H ₂ O ₂	48 h	30 \pm 0.00	§§§	1.45 \pm 0.00	§§§	28.9 \pm 0.00
0.01 mM	48 h	75.5 \pm 0.92	***	1.48 \pm 0.0001	***	13.0 \pm 0.01
0.02 mM	48 h	189 \pm 0.49	***	1.49 \pm 0.0003	**	9.9 \pm 0.03
0.1 mM	48 h	367 \pm 0.00	***	1.18 \pm 0.00	***	67.3 \pm 0.00
0.2 mM	48 h	/	/	1.15 \pm 0.00	***	73.4 \pm 0.00

Significance of Student's *t*-test (ts) and Chi-squared test (χ_2): NS: not significant; ** $p \leq 0.01$ treated vs solvent; *** $p \leq 0.001$ treated vs solvent; §§§ $p \leq 0.001$ H₂O₂ vs medium

260 4. Discussion

261 Phthalates and their derivatives are a common group of widely used chemicals in manufacturing; however, to the best of
262 our knowledge, the potential for *in vitro* toxicity to cells of marine organisms after DEHP exposure has not yet been
263 evaluated, whereas a number of adverse effects resulting from exposure to this agent have been reported *in vivo* and *in*
264 *vitro* in humans and other organisms. In the current study, the effects of *in vitro* exposure to DEHP on the European
265 seabass embryonic cell line, DLEC, including cytotoxicity, cell death, and genotoxicity were investigated, and the
266 obtained results indicate a clear effect in all the tested cellular parameters.

267 In this study, the cytotoxicity was assessed using the MTT and Trypan Blue assays. A clear dose response was observed
268 with a significantly decreased cell viability already at the lowest dose DEHP of 0.01 mM in both assays. Cell viability
269 was lower for the MTT with respect to the Trypan blue. This might be explained by a major capacity of DLEC cells to
270 produce formazan crystals from the metabolism of MTT solution and/or by a better sensitivity of the first assay
271 (Wilking et al. 2014). Even though viability assays display a different sensitivity, both assays agree upon showing a
272 cytotoxic effect of DEHP with dose/effect relationships on DLEC cell line suggesting the incapacity of DLEC cells to
273 overcome xenobiotic damage, which affected their replication and survival. Giemsa staining proliferation assay also
274 showed the onset of cell death accompanied by morphological changes and cell detachment, confirming the significant
275 inhibition of cell proliferation due to DEHP treatment in the DLEC cell line. These results are in agreement with
276 previous studies on rainbow trout and different mammalian cell lines (Erkekoğlu et al., 2010; Bath et al., 2013;
277 Peropadre et al., 2013; Martins et al., 2015; Rajamanikyam et al., 2017), where 24 h of exposure to DEHP resulted in
278 toxic effects and significantly induced cytotoxicity starting at 0.01 mM. Nevertheless, our results indicate that an effect
279 at lower doses cannot be excluded since we detected a significant decrease of cell viability and a significant induction of
280 MN even at the lowest dose. In a more recent study on GC-2spd mouse spermatocytes cells (Zhu et al., 2017) in
281 addition to decrease in cell viability as a function of exposure time, DEHP caused a significant and dose-dependent
282 increase in apoptosis starting from a dose of 0.1 mM. Rosado-Berrios et al. (2011) reported that DEHP and its
283 metabolite, the mono(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (MEHP), caused an alteration in the mitochondrial membrane potential, a
284 hallmark of apoptosis, in Human TK-6 lymphoblast cells. Cell death by apoptosis caused by DEHP exposure has been
285 widely demonstrated (Bhattacharya et al., 2005; Caldwell, 2012; Sun et al., 2015); however, this phthalate is also
286 known to cause cell death by necrosis (Caldwell, 2012; Wang et al., 2013) due to the activation of a transduction
287 pathway involving two different peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor (PPARs) isotypes, PPARalpha and
288 PPARbeta (Martinasso et al., 2006). The current study showed that DEHP could induce, in DLEC cells, an increase in
289 apoptosis and necrosis at 0.01 mM and higher concentrations of the phthalate. The results of the analysis of cell death

290 obtained in the current are thus in agreement with the data in the literature revealing an induction of both apoptosis and
291 necrosis already at 0.01 mM also in the embryonic cell lines derived from the European sea bass

292 **Genotoxicity was assessed using the Comet and CBMN assays.** Results clearly showed the genotoxic and mutagenic
293 potential of DEHP in DLEC embryonic cells. The overall amount of DNA strand breaks detected by means of the
294 Comet assay was not very high, even if it significantly increased at increasing concentrations of the phthalate. If an
295 agent shows no or a low effect in one test, this is not enough to consider it as safe, and the result has to be confirmed
296 with other tests that contemplate all the possible mechanisms through which a xenobiotic can cause genotoxic or
297 mutagenic damage. Indeed, from the data of the CBMN assay, DEHP was found to be highly cytotoxic starting from the
298 dose of 0.01 mM, with a subsequent influence on cell proliferation and a dose-dependent increase in the frequency of
299 MN. This result evaluated under the light of a moderate increase in DNA strand breaks suggests a possible aneugenic
300 effect of this phthalate in the DLEC cell line. Accordingly, treatment with H₂O₂, a well-known clastogenic agent, caused
301 a higher amount of DNA strand breaks in the Comet assay but a lower increase in the frequency of MN, when
302 compared with all doses of DEHP. This outcome further reinforces the hypothesis that this compound could have an
303 aneugenic effect in the DLEC cells. Genotoxicity of DEHP on human and rodent cell lines has been widely
304 demonstrated, indicating several mechanisms involved, such as the oxidative stress induction (Erkekoğlu et al., 2010;
305 Erkekoğlu et al., 2011; Yuan et al., 2017), the inhibition of DNA replication (Li et al., 2014), lysosomal or
306 mitochondrial damage (Li et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2015), mutation in genes, formation of DNA adducts (IARC, 2006;
307 Caldwell, 2012) and DNA strand breaks (Okai and Okai, 2000; IARC, 2006; Caldwell, 2012) and changes in DNA
308 methylation patterns (IARC, 2006; Caldwell, 2012). The induction of oxidative stress due to the presence of reactive
309 oxygen species (ROS) is one of the important mechanisms underlying the toxicity of DEHP and its metabolite, MEHP
310 (Erkekoğlu et al., 2011; Li et al., 2014). Previous studies also indicate that an increase of ROS and the resulting
311 oxidative stress can cause aneuploidy in cultured cells (Fang and Zhang, 2011; Caldwell, 2012; Wang et al., 2013; Yuan
312 et al., 2017). These findings suggest that the mechanisms involved in the induction of the possible DEHP aneugenic
313 effect and, subsequently, of MN formation in DLEC cell line might be ascribed to an increase of ROS and oxidative
314 stress.

315 In conclusion, the overall results of our study demonstrated the **cytotoxicity and genotoxicity of DEHP** in the DLEC
316 embryonic cell line with the inhibition of cell proliferation and the induction of micronuclei as the main effects,
317 reflecting a possible aneugenic effect of this compound. **Since DNA and chromosomal damage often correlate with**
318 **mutagenicity (Bruce and Heddle, 1979; Jenssen and Ramel, 1980), a mutagenic effect of DEHP in the DLEC cell line**
319 **cannot be excluded.** To the best of our knowledge, there are still too scarce data to understand whether DEHP is
320 metabolized by marine organisms, in which case, its effects (i.e. that of its metabolites) could be greater in wildlife.

321 Consequently, to efficiently assess the effects of pollutants on marine organisms, cytotoxicity and genotoxicity assays *in*
322 *vivo* and/or *ex vivo* should be included. Nevertheless, with *in vitro* assays it is possible to successfully predict systemic
323 toxicological effects *in vivo* (Groothuis et al., 2015). With this respect, it is worth noting that, although the DEHP doses
324 we applied in our acute tests were higher than those usually measured in the environment (Ye et al., 2014; Zhang et al.,
325 2018), Junaid et al. (2018) recently reported a maximum concentration of 13050 µg/L (about 334 µM) of phthalates in
326 river waters which is in the middle of our range of treatment. Therefore, our study shows that DEHP, which is constantly
327 introduced into the marine environment through marine litter, is a potential threat for European sea bass and for marine
328 ichthyofauna in general.
329

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335

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